

THE PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF USING THE ORAL CREATION OF THE PEOPLE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Kalandarova Fazilat Tokhirovna

University Of Business And Science

non-government higher education institution

teacher of the department of pedagogy and psychology

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola olis o'tmishda yaratilgan va asrlar osha sayqallanib, bizgacha yetib kelgan, xalqimizning boy madaniy me'rosining durdonasi hisoblangan, xalq og'zaki ijodining ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida qo'llanilishi va bu jarayonda nimalarga ahamiyat berish kerakligi, jarayonni to'g'ri tashkil eta olish haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xalq og'zaki ijodi, ta'lim tarbiya, janrlar, ertak, maqol, qo'shiqlar, matal, afsona, rivoyat, asotir, lapar, lof, terma va askiyalar.

Аннотация: данная статья создана в далеком прошлом и, отполированная веками и дошедшая до нас, считается шедевром богатого культурного наследия нашего народа, написана о применении устного народного творчества в образовательно-воспитательном процессе и о том, что в этом процессе нужно придавать значение, уметь правильно организовать процесс.

Ключевые слова: устное творчество, образование, воспитание, жанры, сказка, пословица, песни, поговорка, легенда, повествование, асатир, лапар, лоф, сбор и аския.

Annotation: this article was created in the distant past and has been polished and polished over the centuries, has been considered a masterpiece of the rich cultural norm of our people, has been written about the application of folk oral creativity in the educational process and what should be given importance in this process, to be able to properly organize the process.

Keywords: folk oral creativity, educational upbringing, genres, fairy tales, Proverbs, songs, matal, myth, narration, asotir, lapar, lof, terma and askias.

Times are rapidly developing. As a result, the process of globalization has been showing its influence on the education and upbringing of the next generation of every nation. For this reason, we should approach the issue of education seriously, without forgetting that the education of the future generation is our main task. Because as President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated, "... in order to stand firm in the world arena and in one's determination, to achieve the goal, it is necessary to move steadily forward, to reform the way of life and thinking, and to go steadily towards renewal." Therefore, in providing proper upbringing and quality education, which is our main goal, we should enrich this process and increase its educativeness with examples of creations that have been acquired and polished and tested on the basis of the experience of our people's wisdom and way of life. In this regard, we can follow a clear and correct path only by referring to our rich and perfect Uzbek folklore.

People's oral creativity is considered as one of the examples of the rich cultural heritage of our people, our people's lifestyle, national and colorful traditions, work carried out with patience and perseverance, dreams, hopes and worries in the simple hearts of our people. ,

expressing dreams and joys, keeping pace with each era and becoming polished.

The works of art, which are considered to be the creation of our people and have been passed down from mouth to mouth over time, are called folk oral creations or folklore (in English "folk" - people, "lore" - wisdom, that is, folk wisdom, wisdom). Genres of folklore such as fairy tales, legends, proverbs, anecdotes, stories, epics, quick sayings, alla, riddles, proverbs, and wisdom are widely popular. In these genres, the ways of moral and moral education of the young generation, methods of education, kindness, love, generosity, nobility, value, loyalty, loyalty, goodness, consistency, hard work, love for profession, honesty, justice, fairness, thoughtfulness, humanitarianism, etc. qualities are glorified and valued, but those that pollute a person, disloyalty, avarice, greed, cowardice, dishonor, arrogance, forgery, lying, greed, theft and other negative vices are condemned. It should be noted that examples of folk oral creativity are very vital, popular and instructive in terms of manners, education and upbringing, therefore, they are of universal importance.

The advantages of using folklore in the educational process are as follows; - Deep meaning. The meaningfulness and logical perfection of the work has a strong impact on the reader, makes him think deeply, and serves as an incentive for the formation of positive qualities. Among them are fairy tales, epics and stories.

- Compactness. It is considered one of the main reasons why folklore is passed down from generation to generation, and it is easily learned and memorized by the people. This is expressed in proverbs, proverbs, riddles, quick sayings and similar genres.

- Simplicity. The absence of highly artistic, colorful and borrowed words in the composition of the work is the reason for the use of folk art in many directions. - Melody. The melodious meaning of the words in the work and the proportionality of the words in terms of content serve to be easily remembered by the people and passed on from generation to generation. These include dedications, hymns, proverbs and proverbs.

- Multiple options. As a result of the times, seasons and conditions in the regions, diversity occurs in the folk art without changing the main content. These are reflected in fairy tales and epics. There are more than ten variants of the epic "Alpomish", which is a bright example of the creativity of the Turkic peoples. In short, the integration of folk art into the educational process shows a positive result in all aspects. It must be done with the right approach, clear methods and directions.

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